

High-Level Design of the Data Fabric

Interoperability framework for data and models

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Executive Summary

This Deliverable presents the high-level design of the Data Fabric to be prototypically implemented for the four Real World Labs (RWLs) in DIRECTED, in order to showcase the technical advancements supporting Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA). This will be executed through improved interoperability, data standards and governance. The findings are predominately based on work performed in Task 5.1 - Stocktaking of the Current Data Context and Task 5.2 - Define the project interoperability Use Cases. Hence, this deliverable presents for each RWL i) its expected data contributions and ii) its data and information needs. Furthermore, the interactions between data and among models within the Data Fabric are presented highlighting the interoperability aspects per RWL use-case. The complete detailed architecture and implementation of the Data Fabric is beyond the scope of this document and still to be developed and detailed in D5.2.

Based on interviews with the RWLs, review of previous work, and workshops with the RWL hosts and participants within the co-design approach of DIRECTED, the current state of data usage, information products and software solutions has been assessed. During this process, WP 5's focus has been on technical gaps and barriers where the DIRECTED Data Fabric could provide a valuable contribution addressing stakeholder's real needs. The specific statuses of each RWL are rather heterogeneous due to different regional and national data providers and different compositions of stakeholders and hosts in each RWL. However, common data needs and sources, such as the Copernicus Climate Data Store, emerged from the interviews and workshops. These general base data will be detailed in Section 2.4, as well as ethical aspects of data and data providers in Section 2.5. The diversity of data providers and users of the Data Fabric is a challenge, but also an opportunity to develop a high-level architectural definition for the Data Fabric implementation required to support DRM and CCA applicable in diverse contexts.

In order to support re-usability and applicability of the software components constituting the Data Fabric, the foundation of these components is open-source, and additions as well as new implementations will have the ability to be published as open-source components that can be deployed and extended free of any charge. The Data Fabric will be based on open standards (e.g. OGC) that are widely accepted and frequently used for geospatial data. The envisioned solution will entail web-based front-end components for discovery, access and publication of data and models, but will also provide endpoints that allow to integrate the new information products into existing solutions (e.g., QGIS) already established in the RWLs. The development of the Data Fabric will be carried out iteratively in close cooperation with the RWL hosts and participants, ensuring that the real needs of stakeholders are best met. It should be noted, however, that the Data Fabric will also come with limitations. While building upon open standards for data and model integration, it cannot be guaranteed that "any" data set can be seamlessly integrated nor that any model chain can be build ensuring meaningful results. The development will be bounded by the priority use cases of the RWLs favouring re-use-, extend- and interoperability where possible and affordable within the project's scope.

The Data Fabric will provide means to document the provenance of information products generated and consumed. This metadata will support the reproducibility and auditability of the information product supporting decision taking. Furthermore, access to specific data and visualizations will be given to the Data Steward, a person in each RWL responsible for permissions (Section 2.2). This will enable end-users to assess input data sources regarding their representativeness, such as with climate indicators. These measures are meant to prevent misuse and misinterpretation of information products generated through the Data Fabric.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
List of abbreviations	7
1. Introduction	8
2. Overview of elements of the Data Fabric	10
2.1 Related work.....	11
2.2 Components and building blocks	13
2.3 Tools and models	16
2.4 General base data	20
2.5 Ethical aspects.....	23
3. Real World Labs.....	24
3.1 RWL 1 — Copenhagen Capital Region, Denmark.....	24
3.2 RWL 2 — Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy.....	27
3.3 RWL 3 — Danube Region, Vienna, Austria and Zala Region, Hungary	31
3.4 RWL 4 — Rhine-Erft Region, Germany	34
4. Conclusion	36

List of Figures

Figure 1: Conceptual view of the Data Fabric illustrating common DIRECTED components and specific RWL threads, Exemplary links with existing data providers and solutions are indicated by their respective logos.	9
Figure 2: High-level white box of the core components of the Data Fabric.	14
Figure 3: Data access components of the Data Fabric.....	15
Figure 4: Flow-chart for the Copenhagen RWL interoperability use-case	25
Figure 5: Overview of elements and data sources of the Emilia-Romagna Region RWL. Green boxes indicate observed data while red boxes list forecasts by ARPAE. All elements are linked through dedicated APIs.	29
Figure 6: Flow chart of the Danube Vienna interoperability use-case.	32
Figure 7: Flow chart of the Zala Region interoperability use-case.....	33
Figure 8: Flow chart of the Rhine-Erft RWL interoperability use-case.....	35

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of global, public data sources.	21
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List of abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
API	Application Programming Interface
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
CDS	Copernicus Climate Data Store
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
EFAS	European Flood Awareness System
GIS	Geographic Information System
GloFAS	Global Flood Awareness System
K8s	Kubernetes
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OSM	Open Street Map
OWS	OGC Web Services
RWL	Real World Lab
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructure
SVI	Social Vulnerability Index

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the technical aspects of the interaction of organizations with the Data Fabric. Those interactions include the provision of data as well as modelling and consumption of data and information products. The results presented in this document are based on the work of Task 5.1 — Stocktaking of the Current Data Context and Task 5.2 – Definition of the project interoperability Use Cases. The complete detailed architecture and implementation of the Data Fabric is beyond the scope of this document and still to be developed. The following principles have guided our work:

- A co-design approach has been followed, i.e. the requirements of the Data Fabric are derived from interviews and questionnaires with RWL hosts and their stakeholders, to address risk and risk governance in the lens of the co-production Risk-Tandem Framework, addressing the multifaceted nature of modern risk (see D3.1)
- The focus of the Data Fabric is to address technical gaps of interoperability and data availability in each RWL to demonstrate the impact of DRM & CCA interoperability
- An iterative feedback loop between the RWL hosts, stakeholders, and technical modelling and Data Fabric team has been established and will steer the forthcoming implementations
- As the RWLs continue to communicate with their stakeholders in the agile co-design framework, the currently known requirements might evolve over time and design choices documented in this high-level architecture may need to be revised. Therefore, the Data Fabric design is centred around a modular approach, that can accommodate upcoming changes.

The DIRECTED project addresses CCA and DRM strategies in the four RWLs within the project consortium. One necessary aspect to achieve these goals is the collection of relevant data sources and modelling of real-world disasters under climate change. Thus, Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 for Work Package (WP) five include: Stocktaking of the current data context, as well as defining the project interoperability use-cases, thereby jump-starting the modelling chain and gathering the requirements of RWLs to frame the development of technical solutions and information products supporting CCA and DRM. This deliverable details the technical aspects of the DIRECTED Data Fabric (see Figure 1) in order to support the project's interoperability use-cases per RWL, as well as the integration of data products which have become apparent through the review of existing solutions and individual interviews and workshops with RWL hosts and their stakeholders.

Co-design and co-production are key components of the DIRECTED project. As the RWLs hosts gather requirements from their stakeholders, stakeholders being relevant actors within the CCA and DRM cycle, responding to, or providing prevention from, disaster events, they then relay this information back to the technical modelling team, as well as the team in WP 5 responsible for the implementation and deployment of the

Figure 1: Conceptual view of the Data Fabric illustrating common DIRECTED components and specific RWL threads, Exemplary links with existing data providers and solutions are indicated by their respective logos.

Data Fabric. Thus, from the iterative nature of this process, requirements from the RWLs change fluidly, and the Data Fabric evolves as these requirements evolve. This approach is therefore in-line with the agile framework, where software is developed in close cooperation with the customer (in this case the RWLs’). The development is done in sprints of few weeks iteratively incorporating feedback from stakeholders on the current implementation. This ensures that the work is done at a steady, manageable pace, in order to achieve the larger goal of the Data Fabric. It should be noted, however, that with this iterative approach, requirements of the RWLs might change over the duration of the project. This is to be expected; as solutions are explored within the Data Fabric and interoperability use-cases, there will also inevitably be further gaps that will be revealed. Thus, the Data Fabric architecture described in this deliverable is based on a modular approach incorporating components tailored to specific tasks that communicate via open and well-defined application programming interfaces (APIs). Hence, upcoming changes can be flexibly integrated into the Data Fabric.

The following Section 2 will provide a general high-level overview of the Data Fabric and provide insights on common components of the Data Fabric. The interoperability use-cases identified in each RWL that will be showcased in the Data Fabric are described in Section 3. A conclusion and brief outlook is given in Section 4.

2. Overview of elements of the Data Fabric

The Data Fabric is the technical core to support CCA and DRM in the RWLs of the DIRECTED project. It is one of the key exploitable results of the entire project and is grounded in state of the art open-source solutions to build spatial information infrastructures. In order to maximize reuse and longevity of the designed and developed infrastructure, best-of-breed open-source components are combined in a modular way opposed to building upon a monolithic solution. Where appropriate, the single components are developed in a cloud-native manner and will be deployed within a Kubernetes (K8s) driven cloud environment. K8s allows running the system on various cloud providers, but also - in general - locally (with limitations in performance).

The key property of the Data Fabric is its interoperability; it serves as a data, model and information hub allowing to link outputs of one model as input to another model in a machine-readable way, in order to deploy workflows of model chains. Neither data nor models need to be hosted within the same infrastructure, however, can be accessed through APIs on-demand and in near real-time, to facilitate user-driven assessments tailored to the users' needs. The developed code will be published freely accessible under an open source license which allows to further extend the Data Fabric's interoperability beyond the project scope during and after the project. While the project aims to deliver a single DIRECTED Data Fabric, each RWL will have a tailored view on their "individual Data Fabric" – a subset of threads of the entire fabric. At its core, the Data Fabric will provide common components to all RWLs, and a user management will ensure, for example, that sensitive data and models are only shared among the authorized RWL hosts. While public data are available, such as data through the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS), it is only integrated once and shared among all RWLs. In Section 2.2 we therefore present joint core components, shared building blocks, data and models that are essential to the structure of the Data Fabric.

The following core user types are envisioned to interact with the deployed Data Fabric:

- General public: i.e., untrained users with a general interest in their personal exposure to actual risks or risks in general. Those users can only consume information products made available, but cannot set up or run model chains.
- Expert users: trained and experienced users from stakeholder organisations in the RWL. Those users can also define and run model chains for their RWL and publish new public information products.
- Data Stewards: dedicated staff members that can add data sources and model configurations and control the access rights to models and data sets.

Another type of users are software developers or IT-staff that would like to re-use and extend parts of the Data Fabric or deploy the entire system. These users are expected to start from the GitHub repositories and provided sample Docker files.

2.1 Related work

Within past and ongoing projects and initiatives a lot of work on data, models and tools has already been carried out in the context of DRM and CCA. During the course of the DIRECTED project, we will monitor ongoing developments and align our work where beneficial. In the following, we would like to mention a few examples which appear most related to DIRECTED and the development of the Data Fabric.

Resilient Planet Data Hub/Global Resilience Index Initiative

The Resilient Planet Data Hub (<https://resilient-planet-data.org/>), formerly known as Global Resilience Index Initiative (GRII), is a cross-sector group aiming at developing an open, standard set of metrics for measuring the resilience against climate related risks. It provides an open, web-based tool called GRI Risk Viewer (<https://global.infrastructureresilience.org/>, previous name: Global Systemic Risk Assessment Tool (G-SRAT)) enabling users to view and analyze global data on hazard, exposure, vulnerability and risk. The source code of the tool is open (<https://github.com/nismod/infra-risk-vis>) as well as the workflows which are used to create most of the risk analytics (<https://github.com/nismod/open-gira>). Moreover, the platform is built upon open datasets (<https://global.infrastructureresilience.org/data>) and allows to download data extracts either manually, via an API or via a Python client (<https://global.infrastructureresilience.org/downloads>). An integration of data or re-use of components will be further assessed.

IFAFRI Capability Gaps

The International Forum to Advance First Responder Innovation (IFAFRI) has identified and described 10 first responder global capability gaps (<https://www.internationalresponderforum.org/services/capability-gaps>) of which several touch the provision of data, information products and technical tools. Discussions with RWL stakeholders in DIRECTED showed a good agreement between their requirements and those of IFAFRI, especially concerning real-time integration of data and interoperable communications.

RIESGOS

The RIESGOS project (<https://www.riesgos.de/en/>) was a research project funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) and was conducted in two phases (2017–2021 and 2021–2024). It focused on scenario-based multi-risk assessment in the Andes region. As part of the project, an interactive demonstrator for a multi-risk information system was built based to a large part on interoperable standards. Learnings from this project will be very valuable especially considering the aspect of model interoperability. As the partner 52°North has also been involved in RIESGOS, related developments in the Data Fabric will directly build upon results from RIESGOS.

RiskChanges

RiskChanges (<https://riskchanges.org/>) is an open-source spatial decision support tool for the analysis of dynamic multi-hazard risk. Although there does not seem to be much activity any more in the development of the tool, it can provide valuable ideas for the development of the DIRECTED Data Fabric. The project includes a Python library (<https://github.com/-RiskChanges/RiskChanges>) and a desktop app (<https://github.com/RiskChanges/Risk-ChangesDesktop>) and makes use of Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) web services to support spatial data. An integration or re-use of components will be further assessed.

UncertWeb

The European FP7 UncertWeb Project has developed concepts and solutions to communicate uncertainty along entire model chains in a machine-readable format. Uncertainty is inherent to any forecast and needs to be made explicit for a sensitive decision taking. We will build upon these concepts where applicable and elevate them from the previous generation of OGC standards meeting recent developments in order to re-use them in the Data Fabric.

2.2 Components and building blocks

Before going into the details of each Real World Lab we will describe general components of the Data Fabric architecture. Although the specific challenges might differ between the labs, a robust and modular architecture has to fulfil some general requirements. The following aspects have been identified for the design of the DIRECTED Data Fabric:

- Data ingestion: Data Stewards have to be able to register or upload new data to the Data Fabric or to update existing data sources. This can be done in a manual or automated, API driven, way.
- Data discovery: users need to be able to find datasets of interest for their use cases. Hence, the existence of sufficient and high-quality metadata plays an important role, as it is the foundation of a user-friendly search mechanism.
- Data access: users and applications need to be able to access the required datasets in a tailored format. Data access to smaller datasets or for direct visualizations need be possible on demand in near real-time, while workflows and models may access data asynchronously.
- Data processing: the required processing includes pre- and post-processing of model inputs and outputs and model execution itself. Depending on the model the requirements on hardware and software, resources might be very heterogeneous and span across different computing infrastructures.
- Data visualization: in order to assess model outputs and to communicate results tailored to various users, from experts and stakeholders to the broader public, suitable visualizations need to be available.
- Authentication and authorization: data and models might be public or private. The Data Fabric needs to ensure that every dataset and processing component has clearly defined who has access to specific data and models. The authorization system should support different levels of granularity, e.g. single users vs. groups or single resources vs. collections of resources. Users have to be able to securely authenticate to the system and access the resources.

Figure 2 provides a high-level view on the Data Fabric consisting of two major blocks. The first block “AuthZ” is responsible for authorization and authentication. Data Stewards can define policies which define who has access to which resources. The “Identity Provider” enables users to authenticate to the system. A “Policy Enforcement” component connects authenticated users and policies and communicates the decision if a resource should be provided.

Figure 2: High-Level white box of the core components of the Data Fabric.

The second block represents the SDI (Spatial Data Infrastructure) components. A central gateway delegates API requests by users/applications to a suitable sub-component and enforces policies on the resources. The gateway is built using standardized Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) API building blocks (<https://ogcapi.ogc.org/>, see also D2.1). These cover several requirements mentioned above, i.e. finding, accessing and processing data. There are also OGC APIs supporting the visualization which is shown in a more detailed diagram for data access in Figure 3. For accessing data different APIs may be used depending on the data type. Raster data, like NetCDF or GeoTIFF files, are accessed via OGC API Coverages and vector data, e.g. GeoJSON or GeoPackage files, via OGC API Features. For time-series data the OGC Connected Systems API and the OGC SensorThings API are suitable solutions. OGC APIs aiming at efficient visualization of spatial data are API Maps, Styles and Tiles, which will also be part of the Data Fabric. Specialised web-applications as well as the access to contents in the Data Fabric with third-party tools through secured open standardised APIs are summarized under “Application” in Figure 2.

Figure 3: Data access components of the Data Fabric.

Beside spatial data there might also be data without a georeference or a spatial extent (e.g., guidelines used in the RWL). The Data Fabric will enable upload and access of these and apply policy enforcement to them as described above for spatial data. The integration with the standardized OGC APIs for spatial data will be developed according to the needs of the stakeholders.

The OGC API Processes are flexible and do not pose any restrictions on input and output data or the processes that can be executed. However, when deploying processes that exploit specific hardware resources (e.g. Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) for massive parallelization of code) it needs to be made sure that the required hardware resources and runtime environments are available. Where feasible, natural hazards models and general pre- and post-processing tools will be made available within the DIRECTED Data Fabric through the OGC API Processes to allow for a machine-readable composition of models into workflows. In order to further broaden the interoperability capabilities of the Data Fabric a link through the Oasis Loss Modelling Framework (OASISImf) to external resources is envisioned.

2.3 Tools and models

Tools and models within the consortium are key elements of the project's holistic interoperability, as the DIRECTED project aims to make models, data, and governance systems interoperable (see D3.1). In this section, we provide an assessment of the tools and models the consortium will use to foster the interoperability goals for differing actors within each RWL where different governance systems play a role.

A number of models are available within the DIRECTED consortium which are developed by different project partners. They range from physical hazard simulation to impact and risk assessment. For example, since SaferPlaces is a pluvial and fluvial flooding model which can simulate flooding at a property level, an output flood map from SaferPlaces could then further be used by the DTU Damage-Cost model, to assess the economic impact of, for instance, pluvial flooding in a city. When local data is included in this kind of flooding simulation chain, the information it provides bridges the gap between different actors in the city. With this in mind, the following list gives an overview of the models within the consortium that are planned to be input into various model chains as required by the RWLs:

- **The DTU Damage-Cost model**
 - Developer: DTU
 - Summary: High-resolution damage cost assessment for overland floods, typically in cities
 - Input: flood depth, sector data (e.g. buildings; 10 sectors are built-in)
 - Output: economic costs per sector (can be summarized on a grid)
 - Constraints: 0.5m resolution coarser for other regions
 - postGIS set-up
 - References:
 - Case study paper: <https://backend.orbit.dtu.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/345700777/1-s2.0-S2405880723000869-main.pdf>
 - Git repository: <https://github.com/skadesokonomi>

- **The SCALGO model**
 - Developer: SCALGO, licensed and free for DTU
 - Summary: High-resolution 3-dimensional maps and flood maps with global coverage. Contains data at 1-meter spatial resolution in nine EU countries.
 - Input: sensor data
 - Output: simple flood map
 - Constraints: no rainfall run-off model/capabilities
 - References:
 - <https://scalgo.com/>
 - Git repository: n/a

- **SaferPlaces**
 - Developer: GECOsistema
 - Summary: real-time pluvial, fluvial and coastal flood risk at property level
 - Input: weather data, building data, land use, lithology building footprint

- Output: water depth+velocities, economic losses, mitigation and adaptation modelling
- Constraints: no rainfall run-off model
- References:
 - <https://saferplaces.co/>
 - <https://saferplaces.co/scientifically-proven-hazard-and-damage-modelling/>
- **CLIMADA**
 - Developer: ETH Zürich
 - Summary: direct and indirect impact and risk assessment and adaptation option appraisal for past, present and future events.
 - Input: flexible; data on hazards, exposure, vulnerability
 - Output: risk maps and metrics depending on the input data; uncertainties and sensitivities; cost-benefit tables and multi-criteria tables; insurance risk transfer
 - Constraints: no physical hazard simulation, but specific models (tropical cyclone wind fields, fast river flood depth forecast, index-based hazards such as heatwaves, droughts, cold spells, ...)
 - References:
 - Extensive documentation and papers: https://www.zotero.org/groups/2502787/climada_open/library
 - Main introduction paper: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-3085-2019>
- **Danube Model**
 - Developer: PIK
 - Summary: A coupling of the spatially distributed eco-hydrological model SWIM and the hydrodynamic model CaMa-Flood
 - Input: weather/climate data
 - Output: flood severities for river reaches
 - Constraints: SWIM is not Open Source
 - References:
 - <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2018.07.001>
- **RIM2D**
 - Developer: GFZ
 - Summary: 2D physically-based hydraulic inundation model designed for fluvial, pluvial and coastal flood simulation
 - Input: Rainfall data (raster) or river discharge/water-level data (at gauging stations)
 - Output: Max flood depth maps, max flood velocity maps, water depth time-series in certain points, temporal flood depth and velocity maps
 - Constraints: only runs on Linux and NVIDIA GPUs
 - References:
 - Apel, H., Vorogushyn, S., and Merz, B.: Brief communication: Impact forecasting could substantially improve the emergency management of deadly floods: case study July 2021 floods in Germany, Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci., 22, 3005–3014, <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-3005-2022>, 2022.

- Khosh Bin Ghomash, S., Apel, H., and Caviedes-Voullième, D.: Simulating the Ahr valley 2021 flood event: a comparative assessment of 2D shallow water solvers for early flood warning, Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci. Discuss. [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-2024-50>, in review, 2024.

Valuable intermediate data products and final results of the models will be stored and made available in the Data Fabric. As a variety of users ranging from citizens to model developers are expected, different views on the data will be provided:

- Access to raw data including data sub-setting via interoperable OGC APIs and OGC Web Services for spatial data and plain file downloads for non-spatial data.
- Access to prepared data layers which can be directly integrated into mainstream Geographic Information Systems (GIS, e.g., QGIS, ArcGIS) via interoperable OGC APIs and OGC Web Services as a remote resource.
- Visualizations via web applications easily accessible by non-technical users including the existing SaferPlaces front-end, custom Web GIS and dashboard apps.
- Map stories, a web resource combining a blog post with interactive map and graph elements, will be explored as an effective mean to visualize past and hypothetical future events to a broader public to raise awareness and facilitate learning. The interactive elements in a map story can be based on static as well as on dynamically updated resources provided through the Data Fabric.

In addition to the models, there are tools developed and maintained by project partners which currently include:

- **Oasis-CAIMAN app**
 - Developer: Oasis Hub
 - Summary: mobile application which allows to record and share loss and damage information after disaster events, e.g. floods. It is intended to support the insurance industry as well as citizens/householders. Discussions with the RWL Emilia-Romagna have revealed that there is a need to provide better tools to support volunteer coordination in case of an event. Thus, within DIRECTED we will check the feasibility to extend or adapt the Oasis-CAIMAN app to these needs. The application would then be further developed in partnership between the Emilia-Romagna RWL as well as our partners at Oasis Hub. Challenges might arise due to GDPR requirements and technical requirements from the RWL. The Data Fabric would then be able to serve data for this application. This application is still to be determined with further discussion.
 - Input: drone imagery, user input from citizens/householders
 - Constraints: could be difficult to develop in compliance with GDPR requirements
 - References:
 - <https://oasishub.co/oasis-caiman/>
- **Social Vulnerability Index tool (SVI-tool)**
 - Developer: UCC
 - Summary: open-source tool for assessing a population's vulnerability to climate hazards such as flooding, coastal erosion, and heatwaves. The tool could be used to compare risks within and across the 4 RWLs. Furthermore, there might be potential to link it with one or more of the above mentioned models or to compare the index with outputs from CLIMADA and the DTU model.

- Input: inhabitant census data, Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) data
- Output: maps displaying the Social Vulnerability Index for a specific environmental hazard with the resolution of the census data. It is also available as Shapefile.
- Constraints: some data may be lacking or outdated from the national census at high resolution
- References:
 - <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/tools/social-vulnerability-index-svi>
 - https://reachout-cities.eu/post_type_toolkit/social-vulnerability-tool/
 - <https://github.com/jamesfitton/ISVEHI>
- **Connectivity Hub**
 - Developer: SEI
 - Summary: open-source taxonomy and visualization connecting data from different platforms through 'keyword tags'. Allows 'search and discovery' to increase context and connections between project data, guidance documents, tools, topics, and the organizations producing them.
 - Input: data from a range of CCA and DRR platforms, as well as European data from the CORDIS database
 - Constraints: filtering which data to visualize and validation and further development of the taxonomy with expert input
 - References:
 - <https://connectivity-hub.placard-network.eu>

2.4 General base data

In this section, we summarize open data resources that are of interest and serve as base data layer for further analysis in all RWLs. Table 1 provides an overview and some details of selected particularly relevant data sources. We focus here on open data sources with a large, ideally European or even global, coverage. A more extensive list of data sets including also local and national data sets can be found in D2.1, Annex 2. Selected datasets specific to each RWL are described in the dedicated section for each RWL in Chapter 3.

The Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS, <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>) provides a magnitude of climate related data. It contains observations, hind- and forecasts of data. The Copernicus CDS provides access to its data sets through web map applications (for parts of the data) and via a custom API to queue and download extracts of the data. In the use-cases of the RWLs relevant data sets are e.g.: the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS), the Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS), ECMWF Reanalysis v5 (ERA5), Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6), Seasonal forecast daily and subdaily data on single levels.

OpenStreetMap (OSM) provides global data on roads, buildings and other infrastructure elements. These data, especially building data, can be used in several models of the project partners (SAFERPLACES, RIM2D, CLIMADA) to estimate damage costs and investigate the effect of adaptation measures.

OpenBuildingMap (OBM, <https://www.openbuildingmap.org>) provides building data across the globe based on OpenStreetMap. It provides two layers: the “occupancy” layer which describes building classifications as defined by the GEM Building Taxonomy v3.0 (https://github.com/gem/gem_taxonomy) and additionally the “completeness” layer. Completeness in this sense means the estimation of built-up area by OBM in comparison to built-up area derived from remote sensing data. The remote sensing data being sourced from the Global Human Settlement Layer, a built-up grid using temporal layers of Landsat imagery at varying spatial resolutions. This data source will provide insight into what buildings are damaged in disaster events, and could be used as input for some models. This service is hosted by GFZ and is open-source (<https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/globaldynamicexposure/openbuilding-map>).

Google Earth Engine (GEE) provides a data catalogue offering a vast amount of datasets including land cover maps and geological maps which are of interest as input for some of the models.

Table 1: Overview of global, public data sources.

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	LINK
Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS)	Gridded (~5 km spatial resolution) global discharge model results at daily temporal resolution with a lead time of up to 30 days.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forecast: https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cems-glofas-forecast?tab=form Historical: https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cems-glofas-historical?tab=overview
European Flood Awareness System (EFAS)	Gridded (~1.4 km spatial resolution) European discharge model results from 6 hrs to 24 hrs temporal resolution with a lead time of 5 to 15 days.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forecast: https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/efas-forecast?tab=overview Historical: https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/efas-historical?tab=overview
Copernicus Seasonal forecast daily and subdaily data on single levels	Long-range outlook of changes in the Earth system over periods of a few weeks or months	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/seasonal-original-single-levels?tab=form
ECMWF Reanalysis v5 (ERA5)	Gridded (0.25° spatial resolution) reanalysis data for the global climate and weather for the past 8 decades and an hourly temporal resolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://planetary uter.microsoft.com/dataset/era5-pds https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview
Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6)	Daily and monthly global climate projections for climate impacts research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/projections-cmip6?tab=overview https://planetarycomputer.microsoft.com/dataset/cil-gdpcir-cc-by https://planetarycomputer.microsoft.com/dataset/cil-gdpcir-cc0
OpenStreetMap (OSM)	Static data on roads, buildings and other infrastructure elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.openstreetmap.org
ESA WorldCover 10m v100	Global land cover map for 2020 at 10 m resolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/ESA_WorldCover_v100
OpenLandMap Clay Content	Clay content map at 6 depth levels at 250 m resolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/OpenLandMap_SOL_SOL_CLAY-WFRACTION_USDA-3A1A1A_M_v02
OpenBuildingMap (OBM)	A building-focused view on OpenStreetMap providing information on occupancy and completeness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.openbuildingmap.org/ https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/globaldynamicexposure/openbuildingmap
ISRIC Soil Data Hub	Open Data set of soil properties with a global coverage.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.isric.org/explore/isric-soil-data-hub

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	LINK
OpenLandMap	Open Data set from historic to recent land cover derived from Satellite data.	• https://openlandmap.org/

2.5 Ethical aspects

The Data Fabric aims at supporting users taking decisions which will affect many people and their exposure to risk by combining and analyzing data from various sources across larger spatial regions with state-of-the-art models. This goes along with a large responsibility in the provision of data, tools and information products, but also in addressing misinterpretation and abuse. The Data Fabric will not be able to prevent such threats by design, but will help to raise awareness and provide meta information to critically question outputs.

Biased data

The information products provided by the Data Fabric will depend on the models selected by the user, their predefined parameters and i.e. on the input data. Hence, data needs to be of a good quality, but also unbiased. Basing an impact analysis of a possible measure (e.g., a retention basin) on a high-quality data set of industrial buildings will most likely come to a different impact than an analysis based on cultural heritage buildings. The Data Fabric cannot prevent users from running analyses which might be based on biased input data, but it needs to be transparent about it. Transparent while the user unintentionally runs the study to reveal biased data, but also transparent in the generated outputs, such that the information products become reproducible. A bias towards specific groups of a population in the input data could e.g., be revealed by showing a heat map of the weights derived from the input data in comparison with a population density map. As the data Fabric builds upon open standards to access different data sources, data can also relatively easily be exchanged and model outputs hence be validated by running the same model chain with different input data.

In order to make the derived information products auditable and reproducible, the metadata of every information product will also document the data flow from the input data sources, through the modelling chain towards the final product.

Biased models

Besides data, also models can be biased. A model bias can already be rooted in the fundamental model set-up, as any model is naturally only an approximation of the reality. However, a bias can also stem from the set of chosen parameters controlling the individual model runs. Through providing means of interlinking data and models in a machine-readable way in the Data Fabric, it becomes possible to exchange models with different sets of parameters, or entire models. This allows to assess the impact of the model and associated uncertainty in the information product derived and to critically question the mostly black-box models.

Sensitive data

While the Data Fabric only stores very few personal information (only those essential to operate it and manage users), it may hold or grant access to data sources with sensitive, i.e. safety relevant, data. Exploiting access to these data sets can, in the extreme case, cause harm to many people. Hence, it is important to equip the Data Fabric with state-of-the-art solutions restricting access to the platform and the connected data sources and model outputs. In the current design, this is reflected in the AuthZ component (comp. Figure 2).

3. Real World Labs

This chapter will provide insights into the disasters faced, their data needs, model implementation, and information requirements for the Data Fabric per RWL framing the interoperability use-cases. Due to different discussion states and timings in the RWL, the use-cases have different levels of detail.

3.1 RWL 1 — Copenhagen Capital Region, Denmark

The main hazard addressed in the Capital Region of Denmark is flooding, due to storm surges as well as heavy rain, cloudbursts and consecutive rainfall events. Throughout the interviews carried out during April and May 2024, some of the emergency services and municipalities have shared their concern over a coupled event consisting of high-water levels in the Roskilde Fjord combined with persistent rainfall. Some physical coastal protection measures in the Roskilde Fjord, aimed at preventing seawater intrusion, can cause river flooding in a situation of increased river discharge. It is thus important to consider the impacts of compound event of persistent or intense precipitation coupled with a storm surge event. Reducing vulnerability to extreme events requires coordination and collaboration between all the different actors involved in DRM and CCA. This RWL therefore aims to better streamline municipal and emergency services efforts toward disaster resilience around Roskilde Fjord within three main facets: modelling, organization, and communication.

In terms of modelling needs, there is general demand for more accurate forecasts given the high cost of mobilizing and deploying emergency resources. Specifically, the emergency services point toward a tendency to overestimate sea levels during events, which leads to unnecessary and costly measures in certain areas. There is also a desire for better models to assess the consequences of coupled events such as high-water levels in the Roskilde Fjord in combination with heavy rainfall and increased river discharge. Additionally, it was proposed that waves heights should be incorporated into warning systems issued by DMI, since current warnings only account for water levels. Free model data, e.g. from the DMI Climate Atlas (KlimaAtlas), and the national hydrological (water resources) model maintained by GEUS – Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland as well as light flood mapping tools provided by private consultancy companies like SCALGO are generally available to municipalities. More detailed and accurate models provided commercially are typically more expensive, and thus not available to all municipalities nor used in climate adaptation plans. In this context, the models used within the DIRECTED consortium such as CLIMADA, SaferPlaces, DTU Damage-Cost model, and RIM2D, could supply important new information to aid emergency services and the municipalities with their climate adaptation planning and Disaster Risk Management efforts.

In the response phase, some municipalities have a staff shortage with regard to Geographic Information System (GIS) specialists. This vulnerability can be exacerbated when events occur on weekends and holiday periods when municipal employees might not be available. Given that some emergency services require proactive information sharing, such as maps, during an emergency, having an open-source and user-friendly Data Fabric, able to input layers of climate data into a map interface, is a further requirement of this RWL.

In terms of organizational needs, the Capital Region of Denmark RWL described that some municipalities around Roskilde Fjord covered by the same emergency service present different warning levels; in other words, the level at which flooding is considered a risk in one may not be the same level across municipalities. This is also the case for the warning colors used, making this information difficult to navigate from one municipality to another. Standardized warning levels were therefore another requirement of this RWL, which could provide a way for neighbouring municipalities to better communicate, and coordinate, when formulating their emergency and climate adaptation plans.

These requirements lead to the main overarching goal of this RWL, which is better communication across and between municipalities and emergency services, in the lens of disaster preparation and planning, response, and mitigation. This will aid in better informed decision-making based on past events, as well as a coordinated assessment during the recovery phase of disaster. A good dialogue between municipalities and emergency agencies is crucial. New climate adaptation interventions must be reported to the emergency services and reflected into emergency plans. Additionally, the experience on the ground from the emergency services during the response phase should be capitalized in the municipality’s climate adaptation plans.

The interoperability use-case (comp. Figure 4) has been framed to firstly address these requirements at a smaller-scale, and then to be further expanded to all of the requirements. The initial use-case (forensic analysis) is based on the 2013 Storm Bodil flood event, where the Roskilde Fjord area experienced high winds, and extensive storm surge flooding, leading to significant economic damages along coastal areas surrounding the Fjord. As part of this use-case, the 2013 storm event will be simulated with: 1) original sea levels during the storm surge, 2) increased sea levels corresponding to the projected sea level rise (30-60 cm), and 3) selected simulations combining precipitation and storm surge events. The combined set of simulations will serve as indicators for how climate change might impact flood risk in the eastern part of Roskilde Fjord, and identify areas that are at a high risk for both economic and other losses. The use-case will depict the flood extent and depths at high spatial and temporal resolution, e.g. hourly scales, and provide an impact assessment based on the different event simulations. The interoperability use-case aims at demonstrating the value of interoperable high quality information fostering collaboration among municipalities and encouraging discussion to revised practices.

Figure 4: Flow-chart for the Copenhagen RWL interoperability use-case.

Input data for the Copenhagen use-case consists of the following; historical sea levels observed at Roskilde (open data from DMI; from 10-min to hourly resolution), projections of sea level rise due to climate change (from the national Climate Atlas hosted by DMI), the high-resolution digital elevation model (DEM) provided by the Danish Agency for Data Supply and Infrastructure (recently changed name to: Agency for Climate Data), precipitation statistics (current and future climate) from the Climate Atlas and/or Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS), soil classification/infiltration maps, building footprints and other asset maps. This information is used to set up the SCALGO, SaferPlaces and RIM2D models.

Model output from SCALGO, SaferPlaces and RIM2D relevant time steps will be used by the DTU Damage-Cost model and the CLIMADA model for an impact assessment corresponding to the original sea levels during the 2013 storm surge event, increased sea levels corresponding to projected sea level rise, and overlaid by hypothetical precipitation events to investigate its potential compound influence. For the impact assessment, the DTU Damage-Cost model requires only the flood maps produced by, e.g. SaferPlaces and RIM2D. This model already has built-in asset layers and damage cost curves corresponding to 10 different sectors, including different kinds of buildings. CLIMADA requires three different types of data input: exposure, hazard, and an impact function. For the exposure input, exposure information gathered from OpenStreetMap (OSM) is used to determine what areas (buildings) are exposed in the different flooding scenarios. The hazard input of the model (flood maps) will be provided by SCALGO, SaferPlaces and RIM2D. Lastly, the built-in (generic) impact function will be used to estimate how much damage was incurred by the event, i.e. the intensity of the impact. This function will also be calibrated/aligned with the damage cost curves developed for the DTU Damage-Cost model based on insurance data (including insurance claims following the Bodil storm).

The impact assessments provided by the DTU Damage-Cost model and CLIMADA will showcase how Roskilde Fjord may be impacted under current and future climate change conditions. At 1-6 hourly time-step outputs, the different simulations will provide insights on how the storm surge and associated floods progress over time, and thereby assert the quality of the models and provide a tool for investigating how to inform citizens and local authorities in a timely manner. In addition, the outputs from RIM2D, which is a 2D dynamical model, can be used to study how fast the coastal areas along Roskilde Fjord will be flooded corresponding to the rise in sea levels in the fjord. Information will show both economic and physical losses incurred in all three scenarios (see above). Finally, different adaptation options will be tested.

Results of the interoperability use-case will be stored and made available through the Data Fabric. Hence, the data can also be accessed through the available open APIs into existing GIS application already in use at municipalities for a further analysis in their familiar software environments. The initial case study is based on fixed scenarios providing the framework for future model set-ups controlled by end-users.

3.2 RWL 2 – Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy

The Emilia-Romagna Region's Real World Lab (RWL 2) is led by the Civil Protection of the Emilia-Romagna Region (ARSTPC-ER), which is responsible for DRM related to climate risks, including early warning systems and CCA planning. Partnering with ARSTPC-ER is the ARPAE Hydrometeo Service Civil Protection Functional Centre, which supports the monitoring and forecasting of weather and climate conditions critical for emergency management.

Municipal governments play a pivotal role in this setup, with several municipalities involved, including Comacchio, Mesola, Riccione, Rimini, Bellaria Igea, Misano Adriatico, and Cattolica. These municipal entities are the first responders in emergencies and are tasked with implementing the municipal civil protection plans. Their responsibilities are complemented by the provincial civil protection voluntary coordinations in Ferrara and Rimini, which provide essential support during emergencies.

At the regional level, key stakeholders include the Regional Protected Areas, Forests, and Mountain Areas Development Sector and the Regional Soil Defence Sector, which focus on geology, soils, and seismic areas. National government bodies such as the Po Delta Parks and Biodiversity Management Body and the Biodiversity Police also play significant roles in managing environmental and biodiversity risks.

HERA SPA, a provider of essential services, supports emergency management with infrastructure and services critical during disaster events. Additionally, the Romagna Reclamation Consortium, which manages the minor artificial hydraulic network of the plain in the Romagna area, is involved in emergency management and the Riviera del Conca Civil Protection Operative Centre, which manages inter-municipal civil protection operations.

The needs identified for RWL 2 emphasize the importance of enhanced coordination among various first responders and stakeholders to ensure an effective and timely response to emergencies. This includes sharing monitoring networks and forecasting tools to improve early warning systems. There is a critical need for interconnected real-time data to support decision-making during emergencies, which calls for the development of platforms and tools for data acquisition and integration, such as automated tools, apps, or websites.

Awareness and training are also crucial, with an emphasis on increasing prevention activities and educating the population. Information dissemination and training sessions are vital to prepare citizens for potential hazards. Additionally, organizing exercises focused on coastal risk and wildfire management can significantly enhance the readiness of all involved parties.

Emergency planning and forecasting are identified as areas requiring improvement. Updating Civil Protection Plans with new data, models, and tools from the DIRECTED project can provide significant benefits. Improving the timeliness and accuracy of data availability for real-time risk scenarios is also essential to enhance the effectiveness of emergency responses.

Current high-level Interoperability Use-Case for RWL 2 – Emilia-Romagna Region

The high-level interoperability use-case for RWL 2 centres on the integration of diverse data sources, forecasting tools, and emergency management systems to bolster DRM and CCA in the Emilia-Romagna Region. This use-case aims to create a cohesive and responsive system capable of managing and mitigating the impacts of natural hazards.

One of the key aspects of this use-case is the development of interconnected monitoring networks. By integrating data from multiple sources, including wind, temperature, and rain gauges, hydrometers, wave meters, and tide gauges, stakeholders can obtain a comprehensive real-time view of weather conditions. This shared data resource enables improved early warning systems and more coordinated emergency responses.

Real-time data and forecasting play a crucial role in this interoperability framework. Providing interconnected observed data in real-time supports timely and informed decision-making during emergencies. Platforms and tools for real-time data acquisition and integration, such as the SaferPlaces platform, are vital components of this system. The effectiveness of such tools was demonstrated during the May 2023 flood event, where the SaferPlaces platform was utilized to support the Civil Protection in rapid flood mapping and early warning efforts.

Enhanced emergency coordination is another critical element of the use-case. By sharing data, models, and tools among various stakeholders, the region can improve its ability to manage emergencies. The Data Fabric will support the organisation of exercises and training sessions for stakeholders ensuring that all parties are prepared and capable of responding effectively to crises.

Stakeholder engagement and capacity building are integral to the success of this interoperability use-case. Engaging stakeholders in the co-development and testing of new tools and models ensures that the solutions meet their needs and are practical for real-world application. Training and dissemination activities further enhance stakeholder understanding and implementation of DRM and CCA measures.

Finally, post-event analysis and learning are essential for continuous improvement. Tools like the SaferPlaces platform can be used to conduct detailed post-event analyses, quantify economic losses and damages, and collect historical event data. This information is invaluable for improving future forecasting, emergency planning, and overall disaster resilience.

In summary, the interoperability use-case for RWL 2 seeks to create an integrated and adaptive system for managing natural hazards in the Emilia-Romagna Region. By leveraging advanced data integration, real-time monitoring, and comprehensive stakeholder engagement, the region aims to enhance its resilience to disasters and climate change impacts.

Figure 5: Overview of elements and data sources of the Emilia-Romagna Region RWL. Green boxes indicate observed data while red boxes list forecasts by ARPAAE. All elements are linked through dedicated APIs.

This RWL 2 view on the Data Fabric is a non-exclusive subset of the DIRECTED Data Fabric. A more detailed description of the architecture elements is given in the following enumeration:

Key elements and data sources:

- Real-time Data/Observation:
 - HERA Radar Data: Provides radar data essential for monitoring weather patterns
 - ARPAAE Open Data:
 - River Level Data: Updated every 15 minutes, providing real-time information on river levels.
 - Radar Rainfall Intensity: real-time radar data showing the intensity of rainfall.
 - Sea Wave Data: Updates every 30 minutes, offering information on wave activity at sea.
 - Rain Gauge Stations: Updated every 15 minutes, these stations provide precipitation data.
 - Tidal Gauge Stations: Updates every 30 minutes, offering tidal data crucial for coastal monitoring.
- ARPAAE Forecast Models Data:
 - Weather Forecast COSMO21: Numerical weather predictions from the COSMO21 model.
 - Weather Forecast COSMO5M: Weather forecasts from the COSMO5M model.
 - Sea Forecast ADRIAC: Forecasting data for sea conditions from the SWAN/Adriatic model.
 - Beach Profile Forecast XBEACH: Predictions related to beach profiles and coastal changes.

Data processing and integration:

- **Data Ingestor and Pre-Processing:**
This component is responsible for ingesting and pre-processing data, both manually and on a scheduled basis. It ensures data from various sources is cleaned, formatted, and ready for use.
- **Orchestrator:**
Manages the workflow and integration of data from different sources, ensuring smooth operation and data flow across the system.
- **Pygeoapi:**
Acts as an API interface for accessing various processed data and models. This component ensures interoperability and accessibility of data for different applications.

Data storage, access and modelling:

- **S3 Bucket Static Data:**
Storage of static data including LiDAR, land use, lithology, building footprints, and census data. This repository provides essential background data needed for various analyses and modelling.
- **SaferPlaces:**
A model and application utilizing processed data to generate flood hazard and damage assessment visualizations. It integrates data from static and real-time sources to provide actionable insights.
- **RIM2D:**
An alternative model utilizing processed data to provide 2D risk mapping and assessment, aiding in the visualization and management of potential hazards.
- **CLIMADA:**
Climate risk analysis integrating various data sources to provide insights into climate impacts and vulnerabilities.
- **SVI (Social Vulnerability Index):**
Assessment of the social vulnerability of different regions, using census and other demographic data to identify areas at higher risk during disasters.

Data Flow:

- Real-Time and Forecast Data are collected and ingested into the system where they are pre-processed by the Data Ingestor.
- The Orchestrator manages the workflow, ensuring data is properly formatted and routed to pygeoapi.
- Static Data is stored in the S3 Bucket, accessible via APIs.
- Processed data and models are utilized by applications like SaferPlaces, RIM2D, CLIMADA, and SVI to provide visualizations, risk assessments, and decision-support tools.

Visualization and Use:

- The final processed data is visualized through various interfaces, including maps and plots, providing flood hazard and damage assessments that are crucial for decision-making and emergency response.

This tailored architecture ensures a robust, integrated approach to Disaster Risk Management and climate adaptation in alignment with the requirements of RWL 2. It leverages real-time data, advanced modelling, and comprehensive data integration to enhance the resilience of the Emilia-Romagna Region.

3.3 RWL 3 – Danube Region, Vienna, Austria and Zala Region, Hungary

Within the Danube River Basin, the DIRECTED project is focusing on two locations: Vienna in Austria and the Zala Region in Hungary. While Vienna is an example of a densely populated and heavily built-up area, the Zala Region has a predominately rural structure with diverse geography. These focus areas in this RWL receive a diverse set of disasters, including: flooding, fires, droughts, and extreme high and low temperatures. This RWL therefore exemplifies a plethora of disasters that occur in the EU, showcasing how the DIRECTED project solutions could be utilized beyond the project's end.

Vienna focus area

Due to its location along the Danube, the city of Vienna is susceptible to both pluvial and fluvial flooding events. Notably, in 2002 and 2013, heavy rainfall caused the Danube River to overflow, leading to heavy damage in the surrounding areas. Additionally, these events were exacerbated by areas with inadequate drainage and snowmelt, leading to intense urban flooding.

Thus, the main disaster which affects Vienna's population and critical infrastructure within the scope of DIRECTED is flooding. Since Vienna has experienced many flooding events throughout history, several tools have been developed in the last two decades to improve fluvial and pluvial flood forecasting. These include: HORA (HOchwasserRisikozonierung Austria, or the Natural Hazard Overview and Risk Assessment Austria), which integrates both hydrological and hydraulic models within a Web GIS to assess flood risks and map potential flood zones; INCA (Integrated Nowcasting through Comprehensive Analysis), developed by the Central Institute for Meteorology and Geodynamics (ZAMG), providing high-resolution nowcasting for precipitation, which is crucial for predicting flood events; Flood Forecasting Systems (using models like MIKE 11, SOBEK, and HEC-RAS), which are employed for detailed river flood modelling, simulating water levels and flows in rivers; ALADIN (Aire Limitée Adaptation dynamique Développement InterNational), a numerical weather prediction model used by ZAMG for medium-range weather forecasting, including rainfall prediction essential for flood forecasting; and finally, EFAS (see Table 1), which aids national and regional authorities in Austria in flood risk management.

These models and systems are part of an integrated approach to flood risk management in Austria, combining meteorological, hydrological, and hydraulic data to provide accurate and timely flood forecasts. Similar models and tools are used in other countries along the Danube, where local and regional forecasting systems are tailored to the specific hydro-meteorological conditions of the area. Hence, the Vienna use-case in this RWL is defined as the following: 1) create a city flood map of Vienna using real or near real-time data leveraging model simulations within the models in DIRECTED, 2) integrate data layers to show the overlap between precipitation and snowmelt, and 3) display flooding scenarios and simulations of a 100-yr-flood, to raise awareness and foster learning by already existing stakeholders, mostly within the insurance sector.

Figure 6: Flow chart of the Danube Vienna interoperability use-case.

Input data to achieve the interoperability use-case in Vienna (Figure 6) include precipitation and snowmelt data from the CDS, input data required to run SaferPlaces, RIM2D and the Danube model developed by PIK, as well as already existing data used in the HORA platform, the Geosphere Austria data hub, or the INSPIRE data portal. The INSPIRE data portal additionally contains data specifically pertaining to the Danube River basin, and will thus provide useful as it does not require additional processing. The data from HORA will then be leveraged to produce simpler and more tailored maps according to stakeholder needs. Additionally, the HORA platform will be compared to SaferPlaces, as both platforms have 3D modelling and view capabilities. Thus, the SaferPlaces platform 3D simulations potentially displaying economic losses could be prepared and presented to stakeholders. These outputs will also change over time, as data specific to the Danube River Basin from the Danube model will be used for model input and visualization.

Zala Region focus area

The Zala region faces a multitude of different natural hazards and disasters. These include: tree loss, soil degradation in the agricultural sector, fires, mudflows, and drought. Main stakeholders in this region include the municipalities of the Zala region, the Water Directorate: four of which are located near Lake Balaton, a lake in the east of the Zala Region, the Disaster Management Authority: a directorate which coincides with each county in Zala, the authorities in Lake Balaton, and the Zala Special Rescue Team. From these stakeholder groups, the ones which will be leveraged for the interoperability use-case will be the authorities at Lake Balaton and the Zala Special Rescue Team.

Figure 7: Flow chart of the Zala Region interoperability use-case.

In Lake Balaton, the interoperability use-case (Figure 7) will pertain to the tourism sector. As the area surrounding the lake is flat and easily affected by heat stress, it has historically been faced with wildfires due to dry summers. Thus, Lake Balaton will serve as an indicator for the hydrological conditions in the eastern Zala Region, as well as a way to inform the tourism sector of high and low precipitation years. To achieve this, flood and precipitation forecasts will be gathered from the CDS API and local data sources in the Zala Region. These will then be fed into the Danube Model to show the level of flood that will occur within different return periods, as well as drought years using the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI). Since the Danube Model is not able to produce flood forecasts, the specific use and integration of EFAS and GloFAS forecast data will be determined. Additionally, specifications regarding the local data sources are still to be detailed with the authorities at Lake Balaton. In the western part of the Zala Region, the Zala Special Rescue Team requires flood information at the residential level, in order to respond to storm events. Similar to Lake Balaton, flood forecast data will be taken from the CDS API and local data sources from the western part of the region to be fed into the Danube Model. However, in this case, the main local data source will be a database run by the Ministry of Interior, a database which is accessed by special rescue forces and responders like lifeguards and firefighters, alike. Responders log event data in this database. Data for the Zala Region from this database has already been shared in DIRECTED. This data will aid in the calculation of flood levels for different return periods, along with flood maps from SaferPlaces, to support the rescue team in training and event phases.

By addressing these initial use-cases with stakeholders in both the eastern and western parts of the Zala Region, the scope of disasters will eventually be expanded to cover the different disasters this region faces, by more stakeholder groups being involved, and increased communications between them. It is assumed that the technical specifications can be derived from these first use-cases and the modular and open design of the Data Fabric will allow accommodating further use-cases as they emerge within upcoming discussions in the Zala Region.

3.4 RWL 4 – Rhine-Erft Region, Germany

The Erftverband, a regional water board, is the host and also a primary stakeholder in this RWL. The Rhine-Erft Region faces severe flooding, such as the flooding event under “Bernd” in 2021 which heavily impacted this RWL and surrounding areas. This RWL’s main focus in the interoperability use-case is to gain a higher general water-competency at the Erftverband, to support local municipalities in developing and assessing mitigation and adaptation measures for future extreme events under climate change.

Currently, the Erftverband publishes observed data from their own network and weather forecasts taken from the German Weather Service (DWD) through their HOWIS platform¹. It shows water levels and runoff from gauging stations and precipitation measurements in the region. However, limitations of the HOWIS platform have been raised such as a limited usability and that the showcased data is not easy to understand for the wider public. With this information, it was decided that for this RWL the interoperability use-case will feature a prototypical centralized cloud-based data-store to retrieve data that is readily available and understandable for the Erftverband and its stakeholders related to water and flooding. This will ensure that the data is set-up for this RWL, and available to either a) be integrated for the user’s own use, or b) combined in dynamic data visualization layers for other uses within the Erftverband.

The use-case then pertains to assessing mitigation measures such as installing water cisterns or green roofs in different extreme weather scenarios at past, present, and future under climate change.

One past base-line are the flooding levels seen in the past 2021 flood event in the Rhine-Erft region. Furthermore, near real-time rainfall data shall be integrated as well as climate projection rainfall data based on simulations. This use-case requires subsequent modelling through the RIM2D and SaferPlaces to allow for dynamic flood simulations and an assessment of the different measures. A cost-benefit analysis also for a probabilistic set of future events shall be included by means of CLIMADA.

Overall, these use-cases will contribute to water-competency at the Erftverband and will be disseminated towards administrative units in the region. Subsequently, the interoperability use-case will be expanded to other stakeholder requirements within the Rhine-Erft region, the water board, emergency management responders such as firefighters, and volunteers and citizens who could be informed of high-risk zones and areas affected by flooding events.

Input data to achieve the interoperability use-case and RWL architecture in the Data Fabric are as follows: weather observations and simulations under climate change from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) and DWD including historical and near real-time data as well as own data. These data sets are then incorporated in SaferPlaces, RIM2D, and CLIMADA. For SaferPlaces the data needs include: building footprints, land-use classification, lithology (specifically soil classification), and ERA5 historical data. For RIM2D, this data includes housing data such as derived from OpenStreetMap (OSM) in the OpenBuildingMap data set, sewage network data or infiltration maps. For CLIMADA, outputs from both SaferPlaces and RIM2D will be used as input to assess the impact of different mitigation measures.

¹ <https://www.erftverband.de/howis/>

4. Conclusion

The high-level design of the DIRECTED Data Fabric is based on the current interoperability use-cases of all RWLs. In line with Tasks 5.1 and 5.2, the data context has been established through iterative feedback from the RWL hosts and their stakeholders in a co-development process. It has been a joint effort beyond the core Data Fabric and modelling teams including the entire consortium, to establish the current interoperability use-cases. These use-cases serve as a backbone for each RWL's data context and modelling chain, to then be expanded on and generalized as the project progresses. The Data Fabric will also entail a Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) as a key component as needed by RWL. This deliverable presents the interactions between data and among models within the Data Fabric. It serves as the foundation for any further technical developments to highlight the interoperability aspects per RWL use case. In order to support longevity and re-usability of the Data Fabric, it will ground in state-of-the-art open source components and its design follows a modular approach featuring open standardized APIs.

Adhering to co-design and co-production with the stakeholders and end-users has been a time-consuming but very important process in order to identify their true needs. As the project is iterative in nature and requirements may change over the duration of the project, an agile development approach will be followed which allows to flexibly adapt the envisioned solutions to the further emerging needs of the RWLs.

The complete detailed architecture and implementation of the Data Fabric is beyond the scope of this document and still to be developed and documented in the forthcoming Deliverable 5.2. The Deliverable 5.3 will further address data protection and ethical aspects of the Data Fabric and Deliverable 5.4 will detail the implementation plan. Finally, the Data Fabric itself will be Deliverable 5.5 demonstrating how the Data Fabric can technically support DRM and CCA through enhanced interoperability based on the interoperability use-cases of the four RWLs.

Partner

